

MODERN STELLAR ASTRONOMY

Orion's Sword Star Cluster NGC 1977

and Planetary system TOI-2796

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Abstract

The problem of the kinematics of the approach of open star clusters and stars with exoplanets is considered. It was found that the cluster NGC 1977, located in the region of Orion's Sword, in past epochs approached in space the star TOI-2796, which has a planetary system. It should be noted that in the immediate vicinity of NGC 1977, the James Webb Space Telescope observed more than 500 free planets and 42 free binary planets. The parameters of the approach – time and distance between the objects – were obtained. For this, numerical calculations of the orbit around the Galactic Center were carried out. It is shown that these objects approached at a distance of ~ 7.8 pc about ~ 4.4 million years ago. This approach could have had a gravitational effect on the Oort cloud analogue TOI-2796, leading to a change in the orbital elements of small bodies located in its outer parts. It is important to note that the observed effect could be the loss of objects from the TOI-2796 planetary system into interstellar space. This work continues our research [1] using SIMBAD data.

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1. INTRODUCTION

One of the best applications of the data obtained by *Gaia* and the *James Webb Space Telescope* (JWST) has been the study of objects in the Orion complex. Notably, within just 1.5° of Orion's Sword there are several adjacent and likely overlapping open star clusters – most prominently, NGC 1981, NGC 1977, the Orion Nebula Cluster (ONC, including the Orion Trapezium), and NGC 1980. The famous Orion Nebula (M42) is also located in this region.

In that work we estimate of the parameters of such an encounter was made – the time and distance between the objects. ~~This work is a continuation of our work – Paper I [1] on the study of the cluster complex in Orion's Sword.~~ We have already made such estimates (Paper I), but took different initial data and got a new assessment. These parameters made it possible to estimate the effect of gravity on the loss of small bodies from the TOI-2796 planetary system. There is a possibility of past and future close encounters of stars with star clusters, which can disrupt the stability of planetary systems. By extending the track of the cluster and star motion in past epochs (~ 4.4 million years), the time of the closest approach (~ 7.8 pc) of the parent star to the planetary system TOI-2796 with NGC 1977 was found. Such approaches of the parent star to the cluster can entail effects associated with the gravitational attraction of the cluster

on objects of planetary systems.

2. METHOD OF NUMERICAL CALCULATIONS

To describe the kinematics of the motion of objects in the Galaxy, we consider the motion of point objects in the extended gravitational field created by the components of the Galaxy. We solve the `nbody` problem for each point object. Thus, a star and a star cluster are represented as point objects and move in space around the Galactic Center. To perform calculations of the orbital motion, we used the `galpy` package. It uses the Milky Way potential `MWPotential14`, described by an analytical axisymmetric model that contains a spherical core and bulge [2], a Miyamoto–Nagai disk [3, 4], and a spherical Navarro–Frenk–White (NFW) dark matter halo [5].

3. DATA

To initialize our calculation in `galpy` [4], we used initial values of the spatial coordinate and velocity components. For this, we used `SIMBAD` [6] with a query for NGC 1977 (see Table 1). We took the data for TOI-2796 from the *Gaia* DR3. The corresponding parameters for TOI-2796 are shown in Table 2.

We first transformed the astrometry and radial velocity data into a Galactocentric Cartesian coordinate system using `astropy` [7]. Note that the sign of the X coordinate in `astropy` follows a left-handed coordinate system.

Table 1. Data for NGC 1977

Parameter	TOI-2796
$\pi \pm \sigma_\pi$, mas	2.521 ± 0.069 [8]
$RV \pm \sigma_{V_r}$, km/s	30.71 ± 0.17 [9]
$\mu_\alpha \pm \sigma_{\mu_\alpha}$, mas/yr	1.2620 ± 0.4640 [10]
$\mu_\delta \pm \sigma_{\mu_\delta}$, mas/yr	-0.7350 ± 0.4830 [10]
α (EP=J2000), deg	83.8150 [9]
δ (EP=J2000), deg	-4.8190 [9]

Table 2. Data for star TOI-2796

Parameter	TOI-2796
GAIA_ID	Gaia DR3 3222453935725951488
α , deg	84.1527
δ , deg	0.8963
π , mas	2.863 ± 0.0147
μ_α , mas/yr	2.537 ± 0.018
μ_δ , mas/yr	2.635 ± 0.012
V_r , km/s	20.91 ± 0.16

4. RESULTS OF GALPY CALCULATIONS

To estimate the gravitational influence of the NGC 1977 cluster on the planetary system TOI-2796, we applied an approach that allows us to estimate the minimum distance between the cluster and the planetary system d_{\min} in the considered time range. We calculated the distance between the NGC 1977 and TOI-2796 at each time step, and selected the minimum distance and the corresponding time.

Fig. 1 illustrates the encounter that was used to determine the parameters of the approach and shows the segments of the computed orbits near the encounter point. The initial data are taken from Table 1 and Table 2: NGC 1977: $x = 8.508$, $y = -0.179$, $z = -0.108$; TOI-2796: $x = 8.486$, $y = -0.133$, $z = -0.076$. The close encounter calculations based on these data yielded a minimum separation of $d_{\min} = 7.79$ pc at time $t_{\min} = -4.4$ Myr.

Based on the initial data from Hunt and Reffert (2023) [11], the result is as follows: NGC 1977: d_{\min} (pc) = 7.79, t_{\min} (Myr) = -8.79. However we correlated the integration time with the age estimates of NGC 1977 and TOI-2796. Approach calculations yielded $d_{\min} = 7.8$ pc, $t_{\min} = -4.4$ million years, that did not exceed the age estimates. The age of NGC 1977 according to Cantat-Gaudin et al. (2020) [8] is 97.7 Myr (lg age = 7.99). Another estimate is 3 Myr by Pang et al. (2022) [12]. According to MWSC [13], the age of the NGC 1977 (name=0587) cluster is 4 Myr (lg age = 6.600). A close estimate was obtained - 5.3 Myr (lg age = 6.721 ± 0.064) [14]. Obviously, the above estimates do not allow us to talk about the similarity of the estimates of the OSC age. The closest isochrone in Vereshchagin, S. V. and Chupina, N. V. (2023) [15] is plotted for an age 10 Myr. The directions of the velocity components U , V , W correspond to the Galactic heliocentric Cartesian coordinate system, with the X -axis directed toward the Galactic center, the Y -axis toward the direction of Galactic rotation, and the Z -axis toward the North Galactic Pole.

5. EFFECT OF ORBITAL VELOCITY CHANGE

The Gaia spacecraft has complemented these studies with the most accurate astrometric measurements and radial velocity data to date. This makes it possible to consider potential past encounters between open star clusters (OSC) and the Sun. A OSC passing near the Solar System can alter the orbital elements of small bodies, including in the most distant parts of their orbits. These perturbations, depending on their magnitude, can lead either to the inward transport of comets into the inner Solar System or to their ejection into interstellar space.

We refer to [16], which derives a formula for the increment of the transverse velocity of a small body (a comet), ΔV_p , over a time interval from $-T$ to T . The derivation uses the law of conservation of momentum and the assumption of isotropy of space. The problem is treated as a restricted three-body problem, where the mass of one of the bodies (the comet) is negligible compared to the masses of the other two – the parent star and the OSC.

The formula is:

$$\Delta V_p = \frac{2GM r_{\text{comet}}}{V d_{\text{min}}^2}$$

where G is the gravitational constant, M and V are the mass and space velocity of the OSC relative to the star, r_{comet} is the distance between the comet and the star. Since we consider

Figure 1. Orbital regions of the star TOI-2796 and the cluster NGC 1977 near their point of closest approach.

comets located near the outer boundary of the Oort cloud, we adopt $r_{\text{comet}} = 0.5$ pc.

To determine ΔV_p for NGC 1977, we adopted its mass as $450 M_{\odot}$, and increased it by a factor of 1.15 [17], assuming a 20% companion fraction among binary stars. As a result, the velocity change of small bodies due to the gravitational perturbation was found to be 0.12 m/s. This is a fairly significant value. Under such an influence, the orbit of a comet located at aphelion would change substantially. Recall that the velocity of a comet moving on an orbit with a perihelion distance of 5 AU and located at an aphelion distance of 10^5 AU is 1.63 m/s.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The approach of NGC 1977 and TOI-2796 could have happened ≈ 4.4 million years ago, that is less than the age of the cluster, which is < 10 million years. Approach parameters for NGC 1977 and TOI-2796 are $(d_{\text{min}}, t_{\text{min}}) = (7.8 \text{ pc}, -4.4 \text{ Myr})$.

Uncertainties in the calculations may contribute to the need to adjust our results. They arise from the imprecision of the input data, neglect of the peculiar motions of stars within the cluster, the rotation of the cluster around its axes, and treating the cluster as a point mass. Also, the effects of the expansion or contraction of the cluster and its tidal tails in certain directions in the galactic disk have been detected (Oh & Evans 2020 [18]). In this paper we took the initial data for NGC 1977 from SIMBAD, so we got a different version of the results from (Paper I [1]).

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¹ <https://www.cosmos.esa.int/gaia>

² <https://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/gaia/dpac/consortium>

³ <http://cds.u-strasbg.fr>

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